

NIR spectral imaging as a tool in basic and applied research, from astronomy to wood science

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Astronomers use NIR spectroscopy imaging to study very distant objects, like quasars, that are difficult targets for optical telescopes since their signals are redshifted into the NIR region. They also use NIR spectroscopy to study the nature of exoplanets in the Galaxy since most of their spectral features are in the NIR region (Rieke, 2009). Plant health can also be studied with NIR spectral imaging, and this technology has become a widely used tool in agricultural research (Tan et al., 2019). Wood scientists apply NIR spectral imaging to study properties of wooden surfaces (Sandak et al., 2016). NIR spectral imaging is even used to improve renewable energy through characterization of solar cell material and mapping degradation of photovoltaic modules (Burud et al., 2016; Bhoopaty et al., 2019). These are a few examples of applications for NIR imaging and spectroscopy today. In this presentation, I will present some methodologies and explain advantages and challenges for the use of NIR spectral imaging in these areas that I have worked with. Some results will be presented, and I will show how useful it can be to exchange techniques and methodologies across the various disciplines.

Keywords: imaging spectroscopy, astronomy, wood science, physics, agriculture

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